

BIRINCHI DARAJALI TAQQOSLAMALAR SISTEMALARI.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10691325>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 10-February 2024 yil

Ma'qullandi: 15- February 2024 yil

Nashr qilindi: 22- February 2024 yil

KEYWORDS

Taqqoslama, absalyut qiymat, chiziqli tengsizliklar, sistema

ABSTRACT

Maqolada birinchi darajali taqqoslamalar sistemalari qanoatlantiradigan barcha qiymatlari topish o'rganilgan.

Ikki o'zgaruvchili tengsizliklar sistemasini taqqoslash, matematikada juda muhim o'rin tutadi. Bu usul, o'zgaruvchilar funksiyalari, limitlar, integrallar va koordinatalar orqali tengsizliklarini taqqoslashga asoslangan.

Bir noma'lumli har xil modulli birinchi darajali taqqoslamalar sistemasining umumiy ko'rinishi quyidagidan iborat:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} a_1x &\equiv b_1 \pmod{m_1} \\ a_2x &\equiv b_2 \pmod{m_2} \\ &\dots\dots\dots \\ a_nx &\equiv b_n \pmod{m_n} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Bu sistema yechimini topishning umumiy usuli quyidagicha: dastlab sistemaning birinchi taqqoslamasining $x \equiv \alpha \pmod{m_1}$ yechimi topiladi, bu yerda $\alpha - m_1$ modul bo'yicha manfiy bo'lmagan eng kichik yoki absolyut qiymati jihatidan eng kichik chegirmedan iborat, bu yechimni sonlar sinfi shaklida yozib olinadi:

$$x = m_1t + \alpha. \quad (2)$$

(Agar birinchi taqqoslama yechimga ega bo'lmasa, berilgan sistema ham yechimga ega bo'lmaydi).

So'ngra x ning (2) dagi qiymati sistemaning ikkinchi taqqoslamasiga qo'yilib, $a_2 + (m_1t + \alpha) \equiv b_2 \pmod{m_2}$ (3)

taqqoslama hosil qilinadi. (3) taqqoslamadan t ning sonlar sinfi shaklidagi

$$t = m_2t_1 + \beta$$

ko'rinishi topilib, u (2) tenglikka qo'yiladi va x ning yangiqiymat hisoblanadi. (Agar (3) taqqoslama yechimga ega bo'lmasa, berilgan sistema ham yechimga ega bo'lmaydi).

Natijada x ning sonlar sinfi shaklida yozilgan va berilgan sistemaning dastlabki ikkita taqqoslamasini qanoatlantiradigan qiymati hosil bo'ladi. x ning topilgan qiymati

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x &\equiv 13 \pmod{16} \\ x &\equiv 3 \pmod{10} \\ x &\equiv 9 \pmod{14} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Yechilishi. Birinchi taqqoslamadan

$$x = 16t + 13$$

ni hosil qilamiz. x ning bu qiymatini ikkinchi taqqoslamag qo'yamiz: $16t + 13 \equiv 3 \pmod{10}$, yoki $16t + 10 \equiv 0 \pmod{10}$, Bu yerdan $8t \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, yoki $16t \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$ ni hosil qilamiz. Demak, $t = 5t_1$. $t = 5t_1$ ni $x = 16t + 13$ ifodaga qo'yamiz: $x = 16 \cdot 5t_1 + 13 = 80t_1 + 13$.

x ning topilgan qiymatini uchinchi taqqoslamag qo'yamiz: $80t_1 + 13 \equiv 9 \pmod{14}$, yoki $80t_1 \equiv -4 \pmod{14}$, bu yerdan $80t_1 \equiv 10 \pmod{14}$, yoki $40t_1 \equiv 5 \pmod{7}$, yoki

$$8t_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{7}, \text{ bu yerdan } t_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{7}, \text{ ya'ni, } t_1 = 7t_2 + 1.$$

$t_1 = 7t_2 + 1$ ni $x = 80t_1 + 13$ ifodaga qo'yib, $x = 80(7t_2 + 1) + 13 = 560t_2 + 93$ ni hosil qilamiz. Shunday qilib, $x \equiv 93 \pmod{560}$.

Tekshirish: $93 - 13$ ayirma 16 ga bo'linadi; $93 - 13$ ayirma 10 ga bo'linadi; $93 - 9$ ayirma 14 ga bo'linadi.

Eslatma. $16t \equiv 0 \pmod{10}$ taqqoslamani yechishda biz $8t \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$ taqqoslamani hosil qildik, uning yechimi $t \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, yoki $t = 5t_1$ berilgan taqqoslamani $x = 80t_1 + 13$ yechimiga olib keldi. Ammo $16t \equiv 0 \pmod{10}$ taqqoslamani ikkinchi $t \equiv 5 \pmod{10}$, yoki $t = 10t_1 + 5$ yechimi ham mavjud (chunki, $d = (16, 10) = 2$). Bu yechimni $x = 16t + 13$ ifodaga qo'yib,

$$x = 16(10t_1 + 5) + 13 = 160t_1 + 93 \text{ yechimni hosil qilamiz. Lekin}$$

$93 \equiv 13 \pmod{80}$ bo'lganligi uchun, ya'ni 93 va 13 sonlari 80 modul bo'yicha bir sinfga tegishli bo'lganligi uchun x ning bu qiymatiga mos bo'lgan yechim qaralmaydi.

Bu eslatmadan (1-misol) agar sistemaning biror taqqoslamasi yoki t_1 ga nisbatan biror taqqoslama m modul bo'yicha d ta yechimga ega bo'lsa, u holda sistemani yechimini topish uchun d ta yechimga ega bo'lgan taqqoslama yechimini unga teng kuchli bo'lgan m/d modul bo'yicha taqqoslama yechimi bilan almashtirish yetarlidir.

Misol 2. Taqqoslamalar sistemasini yeching:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} 7x &\equiv 3 \pmod{11} \\ 15x &\equiv 5 \pmod{35} \\ 3x &\equiv 2 \pmod{5} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Yechilishi. Sistemaning har bir taqqoslamasini alohida yechib, bu sistemaga teng kuchli bo'lgan quyidagit sistemani hosil qilamiz:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x &\equiv 2 \pmod{11} \\ x &\equiv 5 \pmod{7} \\ x &\equiv 4 \pmod{5} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Bu sistemaning modullari juf-jufti bilan o'zaro tub sonlardan iborat bo'lganligi uchun uning yechimini (7) formula bilan topish mumkin.

$$M = [11, 7, 5] = 385, \frac{M}{m_1} = 35, \frac{M}{m_2} = 55, \frac{M}{m_3} = 77$$

sonlarni topib, quyidagi taqqoslamalarni tuzamiz:

$$35u_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{11}, 55u_2 \equiv 1 \pmod{7}, 77u_3 \equiv 1 \pmod{5},$$

bu yerdan $u_1 = 6, u_2 = -1, u_3 = 3$ larni hosil qilamiz.

Endi (7) formuladan quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$$x_0 = 35 \cdot 6 \cdot 2 + 55 \cdot (-1) \cdot 5 + 77 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 = 1069 \equiv 299 \pmod{385}.$$

Shunday qilib, $x \equiv 299 \pmod{385}$.

Misol3. Taqqoslamalar sistemasini yeching:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} 5x &\equiv 7 \pmod{9} \\ 4x &\equiv 3 \pmod{7} \\ 3x &\equiv 8 \pmod{12} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Yechilishi. Berilgan sistemaning uchinchi taqqoslamasida $(3, 12) = 3$, ammo 8 soni 3 ga bo'linmaydi, shuning uchun bu taqqoslama ham berilgan sistema ham yechimga ega emas.

Misol 4. Taqqoslamalar sistemasini yeching:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x &\equiv 2 \pmod{3} \\ x &\equiv 3 \pmod{2} \\ x &\equiv -1 \pmod{6} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Yechilishi. Sistemaning dastlabki ikkita taqqoslamasi $x \equiv -1 \pmod{3}$ va

$x \equiv -1 \pmod{2}$ taqqoslamalarga teng kuchli, shuning uchun ularni uchinchi taqqoslamaning natijasi bo'lganligi uchun tashlab yuborilsa bo'ladi. Shunday qilib, sistema uchinchi taqqoslamasining yechimi sistemaning ham yechimi bo'ladi, ya'ni. $x \equiv -1 \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$.

Misol 5. 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 va 7 sonlariga bo'linganida mos ravishda 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 va 0 qoldiq hosil bo'ladigan sonni toping.

Yechilishi. Masala yuidagi taqqoslamalar sistemasiga keltiriladi:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x &\equiv 1 \pmod{2} \\ x &\equiv 2 \pmod{3} \\ x &\equiv 3 \pmod{4} \\ x &\equiv 4 \pmod{5} \\ x &\equiv 5 \pmod{6} \\ x &\equiv 0 \pmod{7} \end{aligned} \right\} x \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \text{ yoki } x \equiv 3 \pmod{2}$$

taqqoslama $x \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$ taqqoslamaning natijasi sifatida tashlab yuborilishi mumkin. Xuddi shunday $x \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ taqqoslama ham olinmaydi.

Shunday qilib, quyidagi sistemani hosil qilamiz:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x &\equiv 3 \pmod{4} \\ x &\equiv 4 \pmod{5} \\ x &\equiv 5 \pmod{6} \\ x &\equiv 0 \pmod{7} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Bu sistemani yechib, $x \equiv 119 \pmod{420}$ ni hosil qilamaiz.

Misol 6. Quyidagi taqqoslama yechimga ega bo'ladigan a ning qiymatlarini toping:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x &\equiv 5 \pmod{18} \\ x &\equiv 8 \pmod{21} \\ x &\equiv a \pmod{35} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Yechilishi. Birinchi taqqoslamadan $x = 18t + 5$

ni hosil qilamiz. x ning bu qiymatini ikkinchi taqqoslamaga qo'yib, t ning qiymatini topamiz:

$$18t + 5 \equiv 8 \pmod{21}, \text{ yoki } 18t \equiv 3 \pmod{21}, \text{ yoki } 6t \equiv 1 \pmod{7},$$

$$t \equiv 6 \pmod{7}. t \equiv -1 \pmod{7} \text{ ni olish qulayroq, bu yerdan } t = 7t_1 - 1. \text{ Bu qiymatni}$$

x ning ifodasiga qo'yib,

$$x = 16(7t_1 - 1) + 5 = 126t_1 - 13.$$

x ning hosil qilingan qiymatini sistemaning uchinchi taqqoslamaga qo'yamiz:

$$126t_1 - 13 \equiv a \pmod{35}, \text{ t.ye. } 21t_1 \equiv a + 13 \pmod{35}.$$

$(21, 35) = 7$ bo'lganligi uchun oxirgi taqqoslama yechimga ega bo'lishi uchun

$a + 13 \equiv 0 \pmod{7}$ taqqoslama yechimga ega bo'lishi kerak, bu yerdan

$$a \equiv 1 \pmod{7}.$$

Shunday qilib, berilgan sistema $a \equiv 1 \pmod{7}$ bo'lganda yechimga ega.

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